

Predictive Tonic Phase on Physiological Response Using Dynamic Control Modulation

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Abstract

The paper is based on a set of common control motor dynamics and how they can be used to characterise a variety of physiological processes and mechanisms. Most works on physiological control systems offer a state-of-the-art resource that reviews the fundamentals and concepts of classical control theory and how engineering methodology can be adapted to obtain a quantitative understanding of physiological systems. This paper contains advanced procedures that feature applications of control motor dynamics to physiological measures based on non-linear dynamics.

Keywords: Tonic changes, Physiological metrics, Subspace identification, Control motor dynamics, Simulation, User Parameter

Contribution and Purpose of Research

The major contribution shows user parameter estimation processes, and adaptive estimation and control. The paper illustrates key concepts and methods that offer an in-depth analysis of three different physiological response control models (Skin temperature (ST), Skin conductance response (SCR), and Pupil response (PR) that works based on four order subspace identification (N4SID) motor control of system identification. The optimal response control includes the tonic and phasic changes of the physiological responses on a non-linear dynamical analysis that targets biometric development tools. The concepts are simulated and the parameters are characterised by two-dimensional physiological mechanisms.

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0.1 introduction

To understand the concept of integrating physiological measures to control motor dynamics, the basics of physiological metrics need to be theoretically estimated. Generally, physiological measures permit an objective workload assessment that provides a real-time evaluation that follows and allows system designers to quickly and precisely identify usability problems as they occur at task performance. The physiological measurement involves the direct and indirect observation of variables attributable to the normative function of both systems and subsystems in the body. The techniques and tools of these processes can vary, and they are all based on pragmatic observation. The user attributes are derived from some measurable properties and functions of the human biological systems and subsystems. The human body in which these physiological processes are carried out is the Heart rate (HR), SCR, ST, blood pressure, cortical activity, and also biochemical markers.

The subsystem is the physiological attributes derived from the main biometric measures. Normally, in isolation, such variables are not very informative to communication evaluators, but when integrated with behavioural, social, and psychological factors that are associated with communication, these processes can offer profound insights into human perception and behavioural phenomena. In scientific engineering and control theory, subspace identification (N4SID) aims at identifying the linear time-invariant (LTI) state-space models from input-output data format. The N4SID does not need the user parameter sequences of the matrix for solving a parametric optimisation problem and hence the method does not suffer from problem-related local minima that most of the time are unsatisfactory identification results, but standard procedures have built the method to error reductive in nature for higher optimisation. The proceeding section briefly discusses some history and works on N4SID model derivatives (Equation 1).

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d^2x}{dy^2} &= Ax(t) + Bu(t) + Ke(t); \\ \frac{dx}{dy} &= Ax(t) + Bu(t) + Ke(t); \\ y(t) &= Cx(t) + Dx(t) + e(t) \end{aligned} \quad (0.1)$$

The variables A, B, C , and D are state-space matrices, where K is the noise due to environmental factors and other defects in measures, $u(t)$ is the input, $y(t)$ is the output, $x(t)$ is the vector of nx states of $e(t)$ is the noise. All entries are free estimation parameters by default with a fixed to zero value i.e. there is no feedthrough, only for static states of the system. This model is used to generate the impulse in Equation 2.

$$\frac{d^4x}{dy^4} = \frac{d^3x}{dy^3} + \frac{d^2x}{dy^2} + \frac{dx}{dy} + ax + c \quad (0.2)$$

Where x is the input current, a and c are constant factors due to environmental constraints.

0.2 Literature Review

The N4SID methods are rooted in the works of a German mathematician Leopold Kronecker (*Miller [21], Brenner et al. [2], Hachicha et al. [12]*), who shows that the power series can be written as a form of rational function when determining the rank of the Hankel operator which has the power series at its basic symbol is in an infinite set. This rank determines the order of the polynomials of the rational function.

In the early 60s, the work of Kronecker inspired a lot of researchers in the area of systems and subsystems in control theory, these researchers (*Dayar [5], Massioni and Verhaegen [20], Park [24], Kaul et al. [16], Wu and Cui [34], Park et al. [25], Jin et al. [14], Jiang et al. [13], Long et al. [19], Favoreel et al. [7]*) save the Markov parameters (Figure 1 and Equation 1) of an LTI system into finite-dimensional Hankel matrix and derive the matrix the (A, B, C) recognition of the LTI system of space. The major observation is that when the Hankel matrix is the order of the system and the principle of the Hankel matrix leads to a basis of the column space observability matrix and row space of the controllability matrix for the LTI system. This allows for the key space to estimate its process to the system matrix through a basic linear least square method. Researchers like (*Fortin et al. [8], F. Dormann et al. [6], Lewis [18], Oksanen and Sarjakoski [22], Grenander [10], Ching and Phoon [4], Smouse and Peakall [27], Charlton and Rouainia [3], Guo et al. [11]*), derive the extension of the stochastic realisation problem where the knowledge is only on autocorrelation i.e. the covariance function of the output of the LTI system is driven by white noise.

The second generation of N4SID attempts to make the procedure operate directly on input-output measures of the LTI systems (*Viberg [33], Oymak and Ozay [23], Viberg [32], Van Overschee et al. [30], Koch et al. [17], Tangirala [28], Kamwa et al. [15], Sadeqi et al. [26], Garnier [9], Van Overschee and De Moor [29]*). One of the generalisations was presenting the name of the Eigen-system realisation algorithm (ERA) made to use specific input-output measures when considering the impulse inputs. The processes have been used for multimodal analysis of flexible structures that occur in physical phenomena (e.g. space structures). The concept of this method has demonstrated practice in resonant structures through their adaptability to the structures that are susceptible to other systems. A novel impulse or process to the N4SID development was introduced for operating directly on generic input-output data that avoids the first explicit computation of the Markov parameters (*Van Overschee and De Moor [29], Bacciu et al. [1], Verhaegen and Hansson [31]*). Its end-points were introduced by (*Garnier [9], Bacciu et al. [1]*), which

Figure 1: Framework for the physiological control system.

Figure 2: Multimodal biometric measure of physiological processes.

has to optimise the different processes, and recently the physiological concepts were applied in this paper.

0.3 Method

The method adopted in this work follows three preliminary steps: (1) designing the control systems for physiological response measures based on multimodal phenomena (2) conducting an experimental setup with parameters (3) generating data for input in the inference engine.

0.3.1 Experimental setup

The participants recruited were asked to sit in front of a modern PC with an embedded webcam for eye tracking, and simply interact with a set complex design task just to register their physiological metrics. They were asked to place their first finger (Figure 2) on hands-on multimodal measuring biometrics (ST and SCR), while the eye movement was recorded after step-wise and rapid calibration.

0.3.2 Designing the Control motor dynamics

The response behaviour of the physiological parameters was simulated using the concepts in Equations 1 and 2.

Figure 3: Index page with response detected in physiological measure, from a fingerprint detection point.

Figure 4: Detection baseline of SCR to identify both tonic and phasic changes in the physiological measures.

The skin conductance is the reaction to moisture content on the skin as a result of task performance while the ST is measured based on the hotness of the skin as detected from the sensing electrode.

The electromagnetic field sensor is based on a small-scale microelectromechanical system that detects and measures forces surrounding the magnetic fields (moisture content and hotness) in a continuous time frame. They operate by detecting the effects of the response force i.e. a change in voltage in the current. The image of the detection point is registered and the physical simulation of the process is carried out using Equations 1 and 2.

0.4 Result

The captured signal is recorded in times on the analytics used for current visualisation and generation, Figure 3 shows the recorded current from the input signal. The SCR is in red, ST is in magenta, and Pupil changes are in dashed cyan. The pupil response measure is based on the dilation and constriction of the pupil size by measuring the area of its surrounding iris as it increases and changes with

time. Most PCs with an embedded webcam might not be able to detect such subtle changes but the signal processing library in Matlab is capable of cascading the sounding area and recording pace in the area and radius of the pupil is detected with image processing and capture techniques. This process is also applied to the ST and SCR, and each of these responses from the response signal is recorded continuously with time. The program is also designed as a module that can detect both phasic and tonic processes through a moving average filter of the noisy signal. Each response point is detected based on the baseline of the target physiological response (SCR) (Figure 4). For instance, the pupil response and ST are detected as a phasic point if they exceed the maximum baseline expectations of the current. The SCR is in (s) and is equivalent to $x/(30^{\circ c})$ of the skin temperature and $x/2^m/s$ of the pupil response.

The system is also integrated with a control loop that generates the quantified response parameters and user attributes from the real-time signal processing. The parameters are set to resultant attributes after application of the moving average filter which designates the response properties. Figure 5 shows a window with the resultant response parameters and attributes with a prediction projected focus

Figure 5: Report information of input data to the inference engine with defined user attributes and model performance.

(a) Error in response input-output for fixation location in y coordinate.

(b) Performance in power sequence of mapped fixation (X, Y) coordinate of the visual interface.

Figure 6: The performance and error in measurement for all physiological parameters for the input attributes (X, Y) as mapped fixation points

of 197%, which is above the estimated rate of 100% with a mean square error of 0.002%, this is feasible for behaviour

response data for a customized model set obtained from the experimental setup. The N4SID model is both a standard and recognised model that is applied to physical processes, but considering the complexity of user behaviour data is deemed realistic to define the response attributes. The performance and contributions of the attributes can also be computed under the free parameters A, B, C , and D , with each user attribute representing its major contribution to the performance of the model.

The error in measure was tested for two basic response parameters (fixation location) i.e. the mapped fixation on the visual stimuli in terms of amplitude and timestamp. The eye movement on the visual stimuli contains mapped fixation for both the X and Y coordinates of the Cartesian plane, including fixation points, mouse click, keypress, and saccades on the web address, this is an aversive sequence of data matrix that needs complex modelling and simulation to define and interpret the sequences of data generated from the experiment which the analytical tool can provide. Figure 6a shows the error in response data of 0.2% and the power increase of $1.34^{(+3)} dm$.

0.5 Conclusion

This paper investigates the tonic classification of the physiological metric using N4SID modeling by applying the principles of control motor dynamics as the inference engine. The method contains advanced procedures that feature applications of control motor dynamics to physiological measures based on non-linear dynamics, user parameter estimation processes, and adaptive estimation and control. The paper illustrates key concepts and methods that offer an in-depth analysis of three different physiological response control models (Skin temperature (ST), Skin conductance response (SCR), and Pupil response (PR) that works based on four order subspace identification (N4SID) motor control of system identification. The optimal response control includes the tonic and phasic changes of the physiological responses on a non-linear dynamical analysis that targets biometric development tools. The concepts are simulated and the parameters are characterised by two-dimensional physiological mechanisms. The future perspective is to compare the outputs to the deep learning techniques for future modification and optimisation.

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